

The Impact of Working Performance, Working Motivation, and Working Discipline Towards the Employee Performance of Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office

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ABSTRACT : This research aims to know the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park employees' ability to work, working motivation, and working discipline. The research was held at Aketajawe Lolobata National Park office, North Maluku, with 76 respondents. Observation, documentation, and questionnaires were how the data used in this research was obtained. The data analysis used is statistical descriptive and multiple linear regression. The results of this research sum up: (1) The working ability significantly impacts the working performance in Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office, (2) Working motivation did not impact significantly towards in Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office and (3) Working discipline impact significantly and is the most dominant towards the working performance of Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office employees.

KEYWORDS -working ability, working motivation, working discipline, employee performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Working performance is defined as achieving work results based on standards or rules determined by an organization. Mangkunegara (2017) sees that performance is the success of a person's achievement in carrying out tasks, seen from the quality and quantity, under his responsibilities. Performance is seen from the work target and the length of time an employee has to complete it. If the employee can complete the work target at the right time or does not pass the set, it can be said that the performance is good or high. Vice versa, if the work target cannot be completed on time, it can be said that the employee's performance is poor or low. The same thing happened at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office. An employee must be able to complete his job well. Employees' success in completing work, both protection, preservation, and utilization, is determined based on an assessment of their performance. In the last 3 (three) years, the progress of Balai's organizational performance achievements is as illustrated in the following table.

Table 1.

Employees' performance development achievements of Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office

No	Assessment Element	2018		2019		2020	
		Value	Description	Value	Description	Value	Description
1.	Service	81.89	Good	81.31	Good	82.39	Good
2.	Integrity	81.42	Good	80.86	Good	82.43	Good
3.	Commitment	81.50	Good	81.10	Good	83.14	Good
4.	Discipline	81.31	Good	80.89	Good	82.96	Good
5.	Cooperation	81.75	Good	81.15	Good	82.64	Good
6.	Leadership	81.33	Good	83.60	Good	84.80	Good
Total		489.20		488.91		498.36	
Average		81.53		81.49		83.06	
I	Work Behavior Value	81.53 x 40% = 32.61		81.49 X 40% = 32.60 83.06		X 40% = 33.22	
7.	Employee performance	87.86	Good	82.63	Good	86.33	Good
II	Work Achievement Value	87.86 X 60% = 52.72		82.63 X 60% = 49.58		86.33 X 60% = 51.80	
Work Performance Score		85.33	Good	82.18	Good	85.02	Good

Source: BTNAL Performance Report 2020

Based on the data in table 1, it can be explained that from 2018 to 2020, there were fluctuations in the performance of the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office employees. This performance achievement is influenced by many factors that are related to the performance of existing human resources. The work ability factor is one of the factors that have an impact on employee performance. Ability is defined as a person's capacity to carry out various tasks in a job. In essence, two sets of factors make up an individual's ability, namely in the form of intellectual and physical abilities (Wibowo, 2013).

In addition, work motivation is also important amid the demands that employees have to continue to increase productivity in an organization. While motivation is the state of workers who choose to take appropriate actions and perform certain behaviors caused by a collection of internal and external forces (Robbins & Judge, 2017). Another important factor that can make an employee have a high performance is discipline. The absence of discipline in the organization will make the results obtained are not as expected and unsatisfactory. Organizational programs created will falter because the goals set by the organization or company are not achieved. According to Sutrisno (2016), discipline is a person's habit of following existing rules, procedures, or work attitudes and behavior and actions as regulated by the organization, both in written and oral form.

Based on this description, it can be assumed that there is still low employee performance because human resources do not fully understand the main tasks that must be carried out. This hampered the performance and implementation of the programs they had planned. In addition, employees/employees find it difficult to accept changes and tend and are lazy to learn about the new rules that apply, resulting in the low work ability of these employees.

The focus of the problem in this research is as follows:

1. How is the influence of work ability on the performance of Civil Servants at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office.
2. How is the influence of work motivation on the performance of Civil Servants at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office.
3. How is the influence of work discipline on the performance of Civil Servants at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office.
4. How is the influence of work ability, work motivation, and work discipline on the performance of Civil Servants at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office.

II. METHOD

The type of research used is research with a quantitative approach, with the population being all employees at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office with a total of 76 (Seventy-Six), consisting of 45 (Forty-Five) Civil Servants and 31 (Thirty-One) Government Employees. with the Work Agreement (PPPK). Data analysis in this study was carried out through statistical testing, from testing validity, data reliability, testing normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity. Furthermore, to answer the research hypothesis, a multiple linear regression analysis was used, namely the analysis used to determine the effect of work ability, work motivation, and work discipline on employee performance at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Center. Multiple linear regression analysis in this study using the help of the SPSS 25 software application for Windows. The regression equation formula used is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3$$

Testing the coefficient of determination aimed to determine how much the ability of the independent variable to explain the dependent variable to find out how far the influence of an individual explanatory variable in explaining the variation of the dependent variable (Sugiyono, 2017). The instrument in this study applied a questionnaire instrument with an ordinal measurement scale. Respondents answered questions with values or scores obtained from the lowest to highest question arrangement. The indicator measurement uses a Likers scale, where the weights/scores used are 1 to 5, 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (moderately agree), 4 (agree), and 5 (strongly agree).

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

1. Employee Performance

Performance is the success of someone's achievement in carrying out tasks, seen from the quality and quantity, by their responsibilities (Mangkunegara, 2017). Fahmi (2017) gives his view on performance, which is success through a process whose reference is based on a certain period under the previously agreed and determined provisions. Torang (2014) also explains that "performance can be described as the implementation of the main tasks and functions carried out by individuals or groups of people within the organization by looking at the results in quantity or quality according to the norms, standard operating procedures, criteria, and measures that have been established in the organization.". And there are 5 (five) factors to be able to determine the performance of an organization and individual, namely: 1) Knowledge, 2) Skills, 3) Ability, 4) Attitude, and 5) Behavior.

2. Work Capability

Robbins&Judge (2017) defines ability as a person's capacity to carry out various tasks in a job. In essence, two sets of factors make up an individual's ability, namely in the form of intellectual and physical abilities. Intellectual ability is the ability of an individual to carry out mental activities. Meanwhile, physical ability is the ability of an individual to carry out tasks that are determined based on physical abilities, such as agility, stamina, strength, and other abilities. According to Winardi (2014), there are several indicators in measuring the ability to work, which is as follows:

- 1) Skills(*skills*)and skills of employees are a combination of innate talent coupled with the nature of each individual. Indicators of *skills* can usually be seen from how individuals carry out their duties at the appointed time, how creative and innovative an individual is, to how an individual has certain abilities, for example, mastering the field or task according to the level of the position held.
- 2) Knowledge is a person's foundation to be able to form skills and abilities. We can organize knowledge from various things such as existing facts, available information, principles, or procedures whose application can make performance more suitable and meet job requirements.
- 3) Work experience. The tenure and level of knowledge and skills possessed by a person also have an influence and can be a measure of the level of mastery of the knowledge and skills that the individual has related to his work or responsibilities.

3. Work Motivation

Motivation is an effort to achieve job satisfaction by providing a driving force to an individual/employee which aims to create work enthusiasm (Sutrisno, 2016). By that, individuals are willing to cooperate, work effectively, and follow or integrate with all their efforts (with maximum effort). Wibowo (2013) also provides his views on work motivation. According to him, motivation is the state of workers who choose to take appropriate actions and perform certain behaviours caused by a collection of internal and external forces.

Maslow expresses the essence of his theory of needs by stating a hierarchy that composes human needs. Physiology is the lowest level of human needs. Meanwhile, at the highest level is *humans' self-actualization needs*. The following is the definition of these needs:

- 1) Physiological: are basic needs, namely in the form of drinking, eating, shelter, and a state free from pain.
- 2) Safety and security: are the need for freedom from external threats, such as threats from events and the environment.
- 3) Sense of *belonging*: is the need for friends, affiliation, communication, and affection.
- 4) Esteem: the need for self-recognition and recognition of others.
- 5) *Self-actualization*: the need for self-fulfilment to maximize the potential, skills, and capabilities.

4. Work Discipline

According to Sutrisno (2016), discipline is an employee's willing and willing attitude to obey and obey the norms and rules set in his environment. Meanwhile, Sinambela (2016) views that work discipline is the ability of an individual to work in an orderly, diligent, simultaneous manner and work according to the rules set by not trying to argue or violate the rules. Meanwhile, according to Rivai (2005), there are several components in work discipline, namely:

- 1) Attendance. Attendance is a fundamental indicator to measure the discipline or not of an employee. Employees who are used to being late for work can be said to have low discipline.
- 2) Compliance with work rules. Compliance with the rules is one indicator of an employee's discipline. Employees who are willing to obey the applicable work rules will always follow the applicable work guidelines in the company and will not neglect the work procedures set.
- 3) Compliance with work standards. The amount of responsibility of an employee in completing the tasks and work mandated can show an employee's compliance with the applicable work standards in the company.
- 4) High level of alertness. Discipline indicators can also be seen from how alert an employee is at work. In addition, someone who is alert will always be careful, take into account, and be thorough in carrying out a job to be efficient and effective.
- 5) Work ethically. One form of disciplinary action from an employee can be seen in how the employee treats customers by behaving impolitely or inappropriately to customers. This action is unethical and could be costly, so the work is ethically is one indicator of an employee is disciplined in working

Here conceptual framework of research is as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual framework flow

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Results

This research was conducted at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office in North Maluku Province, using a 100% sample of the total population of 76 respondents. The results of the questionnaire test show that the statements of all indicators used in the research are valid ($r_{count} > r_{table}$), the results of the validity test show that the indicators or questionnaires used by each variable are valid. The reason is the correlation of each of the indicators above starts from 0.235 because the correlation value of each indicator is above 0.235, which means that all indicators are valid or valid. While the results of the reliability test are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha score is higher than 0.5999.

Table 2.
 Normality test results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		Unstandardized Residual
N		76
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.87645690
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.070
	Positive	.060
	Negative	-.070
Test Statistic		.070
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200c,d

a Test distribution is Normal.

b Calculated from data.

c Lilliefors Significance Correction.

d This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Source: Primary data that was processed (June 2021)

Based on the data from Table 2, the results of the Normality Test obtained the Asymp value. Sig. = 0.200 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that the data has met the assumption of normal distribution.

Table 3.
 Multicollinearity test results

Model		Coefficients					Collinearity Statistics	
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	6.377	3.132		2.036	.045		
	Work Ability	.546	.134	.333	4.082	.000	.313	3.198
	Work Motivation	.085	.083	.076	1.032	.305	.389	2.573
	Work Discipline	.604	.100	.566	6.043	.000	.237	4.216

a Dependent Variable: Employee performance

Sources: Primary data are processed (June 2021)

Based on the test results obtained in Table 3 above the tolerance value X_1, X_2 and $X_3 > 0.10$ and VIF $X_1, X_2,$ and $X_3 < 10.0$. So, it can be concluded that the data have met the assumption of being free of multicollinearity symptoms.

Figure 2. Heteroscedasticity test results
 Source: Data processed (June 2021)

Based on the Heteroscedasticity Test using the Scatterplot as shown in Fig. 2 above, the diagram above shows the distribution of points above and below zero without forming a certain pattern so that it can be concluded that the data fulfill the assumption that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Table 4.
 Test results of the determination coefficient

Model	R	R Square	Model Summary		Std. Error of the Estimate
			Adjusted R Square		
1	1.922 ^a	.850		.844	2,936

a Predictors: (Constant), Work Discipline, Work Motivation, Work Ability

b Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Data processed (June 2021)

Based on the results from Table 4 above based on the table Summary model obtained by the value of Adj. R Square of 0.844 which means that the variables X_1 (Ability), X_2 (Motivation), and X_3 (Discipline) affect the Y variable (Performance) by 84.4%, and the remaining 15.6% of the Y variable is influenced by independent variables outside this research.

Table 5.
 Results of regression

		Coefficients				
Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6377	3132		2036	.045
	Job Skills	.546	.134	.333	4,082	.000
	Work Motivation	.085	.083	.076	1.032	.305
	Work Discipline	.604	.100	.566	6043	.000

a Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Data processed (June 2021)

In Table 5. above, the results of the calculation of independent variables can be arranged in a model as follows:

$$Y = 6.377 + 0.546 X_1 + 0.085 X_2 + 0.604 X_3$$

Information:

Y = Employee Performance

X₁ = Work Ability

X₂ = Work Motivation

X₃ = Work Discipline The

Results of the analysis can be interpreted as follows:

- 1) The constant value of the equation above is 6,377; the number indicates that if X₁ (Work Ability), X₂ (Work Motivation), X₃ (Discipline) Work is constant or X = 0, then the performance is 6377. This means that every 1% increase in the independent variable will positively affect the dependent variable of 6,377%.
- 2) X₁ (Work Ability) shows the coefficient value of (0.546). If there is an increase in work ability of 1%, the employee's performance will also increase by 0.546 with the multiplier variable assuming the other independent variables are considered constant.
- 3) X₂ (Work Motivation) shows a coefficient value of (0.085), so if there is an increase in work motivation of 1%, the employee's performance will also increase by 0.085 with the multiplier variable assuming the other independent variables are considered constant.
- 4) X₃ (Work Discipline) shows a coefficient value of (0.604); this means that if there is an increase in work discipline by 1%, the employee's performance will also increase by the multiplier variable (0.604), assuming the other independent variables are considered constant.

Table 6.
 T-test results (partial)

		Coefficients				
Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6377	3132		2036	.045
	Job Skills	.546	.134	.333	4,082	.000
	Work Motivation	.085	.083	.076	1.032	.305
	Work Discipline	.604	.100	.566	6043	.000

a Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Data processed (June 2021)

From the results of the t test in Table 6 above, it can be explained as follows:

- 1) The results of the t test for workability X_1 obtained: $t_{arithmetic} (4.082) > t_{table} (1.993)$, which has a sig value. $X_1 = 0.000 < 0.05$, so the result can conclude that the workability variable (X_1) **has a significant effect** on employee performance, so the first hypothesis in this study is **accepted**.
- 2) The results of the t test for work motivation X_2 obtained: $t_{count} (1.032) < t_{table} (1.993)$ which has a sig. $X_2 = 0.305 > 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the work motivation variable (X_2) does **not significantly affect** employee performance, then the second hypothesis in this study is **rejected**.
- 3) The results of the t test for work discipline X_3 obtained: $t_{arithmetic} (6.043) > t_{table} (1.993)$, which has a sig value. $X_1 = 0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the work discipline variable (X_3) **has a significant effect** on employee performance, so the third hypothesis in this study is **accepted**.

To determine the effect of each independent variable, namely Work Ability (X_1), Work Motivation (X_2), and Work Discipline (X_3) on Employee Performance (Y) at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Hall, then Table 4.15 above can be explained as follows:

- 1) $\beta_1 = 0.333$, then this indicates that the influence of the Civil Service Job Skills on the performance of employees of the National Park Aketajawe Lolobata is equal to 33.3%.
- 2) $\beta_2 = 0.076$, then it shows that the influence of work motivation on employee performance hall National Parks Aketajawe Lolobata is equal to 7.6%.
- 3) $\beta_3 = 0.566$, then it shows the influence of employees' performance Work Discipline of the National Park Aketajawe Lolobata is equal to by 56.6%.

Based on the description above, it can be seen that the three variables, the Work Discipline variable (X_3 Yes), has a dominant influence in improving the performance of the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Employees. The beta number or *standardized coefficient* of X_3 is 0.566, which means it is greater than the variables X_1 (0.333) and X_2 (0.076).

Table. 7.
 F test results (simultaneous)

Model	Sum of Squares	ANOVA ^a			F	Sig.
		df	Mean Square			
1	Regression	3517,805	3	1172,602	136,052	000 ^b
	Residual	620,550	72	8,619		
	Total	4138,355	75			

a Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b Predictors: (Constant), Work Discipline, Work Motivation, Work Ability

Source: Data processed (June 2021)

- 4) Based on the results of Table 9 above can be explained as follows:
 The results of the f test can be obtained data that $f_{count} (136.052) > f_{table} (2.73)$ which has a value of sig = $0.000 < 0.05$ then based on the Anova table above, it can be concluded that X_4 (variable X_1 , X_2 , and X_3) **jointly significant effect** on Y.

2. Discussion

2.1. The influence of work ability on employee performance

The results of hypothesis testing have proven that there is an influence between work ability on employee performance. The test results statistically prove that the Work Ability variable *has a significant effect* on the Performance of Civil Servants at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Hall. Work Ability is an individual's ability to carry out work, both physical and intellectual work, to contribute to the effectiveness and success of the organization. The results of this study are an indicator of the ability to work are skills, knowledge and work experience, of three indicators of respondents provide an assessment of the ability of the highest job is

to work experience so that the results of the t test (partial) that work ability has a significant effect on employee performance. Work ability has a significant influence: employees have excellent skills, knowledge, and work experience. By the work experience, the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Hall employees have employees who have worked for more than 10 years. This proves that work experience is very influential on the performance of an organization; the more employees have work experience, the better employee performance.

This research is in line with research conducted by Sinaga (2019) entitled *The Influence of Ability, Motivation and Environment on employee performance (case study at PT. PLN Persero UP3 Yogyakarta)*, This study aims to determine the effect of ability and motivation on employee performance at PT. PLN Persero UP3 Yogyakarta. The method used in this study using quantitative research methods. And the sample used in this study were 80 respondents. Based on the multiple linear regression analysis results, it is found that the most dominant factor influencing employee performance is work ability. This is evidenced by the value *standardized coefficient* largest. Ability has a significant effect on employee performance. The better the ability, the employee's performance will increase. Ability has a positive effect on employee performance, meaning that if the ability is getting better, then employee performance will increase.

2.2. The effect of work motivation on employee performance

Statistical testing proves that the variable *motivation has an insignificant but not significant effect on the performance* of the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office. This indicates that there is a relationship but no significant effect between work motivation and employee performance, in the sense that if work motivation increases, the performance of employees remains. Indicators of the influence of work motivation are Physical Needs, Sense of Security, Social Needs, Appreciation, and Self-Actualization. Of the five indicators, the lowest value is the Physical Needs indicator, including additional income if working beyond office standards (diligent).

Based on the low indicators of the Physical Needs variable above, it indicates that the leadership's attention to staff has not been maximized regarding rewards and punishments for employee performance which reduces work motivation, employees do not feel additional income from outside the salary earned so that it makes employee performance low and causes organizational performance also low. This study is not in line with research conducted by Humaira (2018) entitled *Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai di Kantor Badan Kepegawaian Kota Binjai* (The Effect of Work Motivation and Work Discipline on Employee Performance at the Office of the Binjai City Personnel Agency), using work motivation and work discipline as independent variables and employee performance as the dependent variable. The analysis was carried out using the Multiple Regression and Correlation method. While the hypothesis test using t test and F test, with $\alpha = 0.05$. The hypothesis in this study is that work motivation and work discipline have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Binjai City Personnel Agency.

2.3. The influence of work ability, work motivation and work discipline on employee performance together

Based on the F (simultaneous) test results above, *work ability, work motivation, and discipline jointly affect employee performance*. This is what happened to employees at the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Hall that work ability, work motivation, and work discipline affected employee performance. This shows that the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Office employees have Human Resources internally, have the ability to work, the motivation that arises within themselves to develop, and the desire to be better in the discipline.

V. CONCLUSION

Thus, good and bad work skills and work discipline of employees will affect employees' good and bad performance in the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Hall. The results of partial statistical calculations show that work motivation does not have a significant effect, it is possible because the indicator of physical need for additional income from outside the salary is considered very less given by the office received by the employee, so it gets a low score by the employee. While the statistical results simultaneously work ability, work motivation, and work discipline have a significant effect on employee performance. So that good and bad work

ability, work motivation, and work discipline of employees together will affect employees' good and bad performance. Thus, these three factors support each other to realize low and high employee performance in this organization.

The results of the study also show that there are aspects that need to be considered in each variable, namely:

1. Regarding work ability, the three indicators are Skills, Knowledge, and Work Experience, the understanding of employees is still lacking in the problems that surround the work results in a quality satisfactory to the leadership, the quantity of work is still normal, and innovation in work is still lacking. These problems are included in the skills indicator.
2. Related to work motivation, the indicators are Physical Needs, Sense of Security, Social Needs, Appreciation, and Self-Actualization. The problems that arise are the lack of salary received following the position, lack of salary received to meet daily needs, and additional income outside salaries received by employees are still low. These problems are included in the Physical Needs indicator.
3. Related to work discipline, the indicators are Attendance, Punctuality, Obedience, and Use of office equipment, problems that arise are the lack of understanding of employees regarding the use of office uniforms by office rules, lack of compliance by employees in the use of identification/identity, and lack of employees in obeying and comply with rules. Furthermore, all of that is included in the indicators of obedience.

Suggestion

Based on the conclusions above, researchers can provide suggestions to improve the performance of employees in the Aketajawe Lolobata National Park Hall as follows:

1. Regarding the aspect of work ability.
 - a) It is expected that the leaders or superiors can improve the work ability of employees through a combination of activities between old employees and new employees so that things can improve employee performance. This can be done by assigning a team between old employees and new employees to create learning between employees.
 - b) It is expected that the leadership or superiors can improve the work ability of employees by carrying out building activities for all staff. It is possible to carry out internal education and training activities or send personnel or employees to education and training centers to learn, especially technical training adjusted to the job level so that employees can improve their abilities at their job level.
 - c) Expect leaders or superiors to improve the work ability of employees by improving the quality of employees in carrying out and completing jobs that are the burden of their respective duties. In this case, special training and technical training related to their respective jobs can be carried out to improve their abilities properly related to work in their fields.
2. On the aspect of work motivation.
 - a) It is hoped that the leaders or superiors can increase employee motivation by carrying out awarding activities for employees who excel in encouraging employees to be even more enthusiastic at work.
 - b) It is expected that leaders or superiors can increase employee work motivation by explaining or understanding to employees of the applicable payroll system, especially regarding the payroll system and benefits determined from the center. In addition, it is also necessary to pay attention to the payment of employees that have been received so far, namely by providing honoraria or additional work wages for employees who excel or who do work that exceeds their workload, so that employees are encouraged to increase motivation in carrying out their duties to work.
3. On the aspect of work discipline
 - a) It is expected that leaders or superiors can improve work discipline through continuous outreach activities to employees to increase understanding of the rules and regulations that apply in the organization, including how to dress. In this case, it can be done by distributing manuals/guidelines, brochures and posting rules and regulations in strategic places in the office environment. Employees are always encouraged to be more disciplined.

- b) It is expected that the leaders or superiors can improve work discipline by giving penalties so that employees who violate will be deterred and will not repeat it.
4. Regarding employee performance aspects
- a) It is expected that the leaders or superiors can improve the work discipline of employees by enforcing a clear reward and punishment system within the organization so that employees who are diligent and achievers receive greater rewards than employees who are not diligent or lazy.
- b) It is expected that leaders or superiors can improve employee performance by fostering a safe and conducive work environment, creating harmonious communication among all organization members, both superiors and subordinates. It can be realized through regular meetings or meetings for a certain period or sports and arts events to establish intimacy among all employees or superiors.
- c) It is expected that leaders or superiors can improve the performance of their employees by placing employees under their positions, in the sense that functional officials who incidentally have to work in the field are not placed in the position of budget manager who incidentally is in the hall office. In order for the performance of employees to increase because they are placed in work positions that are in accordance with their abilities in their fields.

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